

EnergyMeasures

Tailored measures supporting energy vulnerable households

D4.5

Review of structural initiatives for addressing energy poverty

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February 2024

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Table of Contents

About EnergyMeasures	5
1 Introduction.....	8
1.1 What do we mean by internal and external capacity building?.....	8
1.2 Why is capacity building an important topic?.....	9
1.3 Connections to other activities and tasks in the EnergyMeasures project.....	10
1.4 Methodology	10
1.5 Reading Guide.....	11
2 Internal capacity building	11
2.1 General figures on EnergyMeasures.....	11
2.2 Internal capacity building within the participating countries	12
2.3 Internal capacity building within the consortium	14
2.4 Contribution to alleviating energy poverty.....	15
3 External capacity building.....	15
3.1 General figures on behaviour change as a result of the EnergyMeasures project	15
3.2 External capacity building within the participating countries.....	16
3.3 Contribution to alleviating energy poverty.....	29
4 Monitoring of structural initiatives.....	29
4.1 Structural initiatives developed from the EnergyMeasures project	37
5 Concluding remarks	42
6 References.....	43

About EnergyMeasures

EnergyMeasures is working to address energy poverty in seven European countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland and the United Kingdom. The project comprises two complementary and synergistic strands of work.

The first strand involves working with energy poor households to improve their energy efficiency through a combination of low-cost measures, and changes in energy-related behaviours and practices. Recruited householders will be provided with low-cost energy measures and empowered to change their energy-related behaviours and practices through an approach that takes account of existing housing conditions and is reflective of their lived experience.

The second strand comprises working with municipalities, energy authorities, housing associations and other relevant actors to assess how current multi-level institutional contexts affect efforts to alleviate energy vulnerability in the participating countries. This knowledge will be used to develop and support the implementation of policy and practice measures which will address structural issues that combine to trap households in energy poverty.

Through this work the project contributes to reducing participants' vulnerability to energy poverty, while at the same time cutting household energy consumption and associated GHG emissions.

For more information see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

The aim of this deliverable is to evaluate how the capacity building steps taken by the partners contribute to alleviating energy poverty in their country. To complete this evaluation, we have taken several steps. From quantifying the internal and external capacity building per participating partner/participating country, to an evaluation of the participatory co-production methods that have been discussed in extensively in WP3. Task 4.3 of work package 4 involves a summarising of the work package, in which knowledge gained in work packages 2, 3, 5 and 6 is quantified. Notably, section 4 of the deliverable deals with the evaluation of innovative policy measures that have emerged from the EnergyMeasures project. This deliverable also draws heavily from the knowledge and lessons learned in work package 3.

Glossary

CSA	Coordination and support action
DoA	Description of Action
EA	Energy Action
EC	European Commission
EM	EnergyMeasures
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
SvP	The Society of St. Vincent de Paul
T	Task
TIG	Tighean Innse Gall
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This final work package deliverable reports on the work carried out in the context of Task 4.3 “Monitoring structural initiatives”. The first objective of T4.3 was to assess the internal and external capacity building initiatives within the project, such as the internal training and upskilling (notably the household recruitment and engagement efforts in WP2) and the participatory co-production methods used in work packages 3 and 5, in addition to the knowledge transfer activities in WP6¹. This effort was captured by quantifying the amount of people engaged across the various project activities in the different participating countries, as well as characterising the nature and scope of capacity-building, along with the number of participants with increased skills, capabilities and competencies as a result of these engagements. The second objective has been to provide an evaluation of the governance and policy innovations arising from the work of the project, as they have been informed by the structural initiatives designed to tackle energy poverty. While WP4 is a standalone work package, it is closely linked to T3.1 and T3.2 of WP3 (Policy and practice innovation) that have been primarily focused on understanding innovative policy adjustments and capacity building. The second question of T4.3 is in fact an extension of these two tasks. Within WP3, we have looked at several innovative initiatives aimed at alleviating energy poverty. Therefore, we looked at multi-layered policies to address both structural problems and aspects of household energy needs related to energy poverty. In this report we provide an overview of these innovative initiatives (described in D3.1 and D3.2), with a focus on the capacity building achieved to help achieve the structural changes needed within the energy poverty policy field. We also demonstrate how the EnergyMeasures project has contributed to structural policy adjustments designed to alleviate energy poverty in all countries at different scales.

1.1 What do we mean by internal and external capacity building?

In sections 2 and 3 of this report, we discuss in detail the capacity building initiatives that took place within the project. However, before doing this, it is important to clearly define what we mean by the term.

INTERNAL CAPACITY BUILDING

Internal capacity building is about knowledge building within an organisation or group. In this project, we distinguish internal capacity building at various levels. Firstly, this refers to internal capacity building within the consortium as a whole. When forming a consortium, it cannot be assumed that every partner has the same levels or types of knowledge and skills even if all partners have knowledge and experience with the subject. Also, given the dynamic nature of work environments and the organisations within the consortium those initially contributing to the work effort may leave the project due to promotion, retirement, illness, etc., or move on to different projects within their own organisation. Internal capacity building, therefore, refers to the process of ensuring all partners reach the same level of knowledge to the meet project objectives in an informed and coherent manner. Secondly, it concerns knowledge building with a individual partners or among a specific group of partners from the same country (e.g., what we refer to elsewhere as the Belgium cluster and the Netherlands cluster). Examples include sharing knowledge about the scope of energy poverty within the participating partner countries and about the specificities informing key issues

¹ While Oikoplus did not lead any specific activities in WP4, their work informed and supported the other partners in the project’s capacity building efforts.

regarding energy poverty in each respective country. Another example would be the establishing and setting up a train-the-trainer process in which employees of a partner organisation are offered skills and knowledge so that they can then start working within the project in a more targeted and informed way.

EXTERNAL CAPACITY BUILDING

We also distinguish between three forms of external capacity building. Firstly, we look at external capacity building among professionals. These may be policy officers who work at municipalities, but also employees of housing associations, politicians, board members of an energy cooperative or social organisations. During the EnergyMeasures project, project partners went through several 'phases' to bring the project, its results and possible policy interventions to the attention of a diverse group of stakeholders. This included in-person workshops, online webinars, giving presentations at conferences and/or giving guest lectures at educational institutions. Secondly, the project has by design contributed to knowledge building among the households involved in the project. Through interventions carried out in the participating countries, households have built up knowledge about topics such as energy savings, behavioural change potentials, how their energy bill is structured and how they can best read and understand the information presented in their bills. Additionally, households gained knowledge on related topics, such as 'where can I ask for help with my difficult financial situation'. The last form of external capacity building relates to energy poverty policy and the institutional and societal contexts within which the EnergyMeasures project operated. Through workshops in various partner countries, we investigated what opportunities and obstacles (some unintentionally) can result from existing (energy) policies and regulations, and how the project can potentially contribute to supporting energy poor households through measures that are both applicable to individual circumstances and effective. During the project, successful new collaborations with the aim of reducing energy poverty started in some countries and will most likely continue after the end of this project. The EnergyMeasures project has contributed to several positive policy adjustments at different levels of government.

1.2 Why is capacity building an important topic?

A large part of the interventions and results of the EnergyMeasures project have been qualitative. Firstly, given the nature and scale of the issue, a significant portion of the interventions were aimed at increasing awareness among households by giving them bespoke, personal guidance in understanding their energy bills, implementing (relatively) low-cost energy-saving measures, and reducing their energy consumption in a responsible manner that does not cause them greater harm. In addition, several partners have spent a substantial amount of time informing citizens about potential energy saving options they could avail of. This included energy clinics, information sessions in libraries, road shows, involving students in energy projects and the like. In order to increase people's awareness of their energy consumption and to help them take positive steps to address their own potentially excessive consumption behaviours, an informed understanding of energy saving is necessary.

There is also a strong qualitative component on the part of the project that focused on identifying policies to alleviate energy poverty. Workshops involving stakeholders like policymakers and representatives of energy companies were held in all partner countries to investigate, for example, how to jointly influence policy at

different scales of government (*e.g.*, local, regional, and national). A significant outcome of these workshops has been knowledge building and networking where participants are now better able to link up with the right person in each of the participating organisations. It is therefore important to work on both internal (*i.e.*, across the consortium and within the partner organisations) and external (*i.e.*, among professionals/households/policy actors, *etc.*) capacity building within a project that has a strong qualitative approach such as EnergyMeasures. Ultimately, it is important for anyone who is involved in alleviating energy poverty in any way, that they have the most up-to-date and pertinent knowledge available. This has been the rationale informing the project's approach from the beginning.

1.3 Connections to other activities and tasks in the EnergyMeasures project

Work package 4 is primarily concerned with *Impact Quantification*. T4.1 and T4.2 deal with energy savings, including the changes in electrical energy demand and thermal energy demand; any reductions in the numbers of households living in energy poverty; and how households have managed to reduce their energy consumption by changing their behaviour. As mentioned, this deliverable connects to and is informed by effort in WP3, because of the partly overlapping themes. If we look at internal and external capacity building, we also see relationships with WP2 through external capacity building in efforts to guide and inform households affected by energy poverty, and internal capacity building by increasing the knowledge base of consortium partners. Also, the interlinking effort in WP6 through external capacity building by organising workshops and knowledge sessions among professionals.

1.4 Methodology

The approach taken for this deliverable has been to incorporate contributions from all participating partners. The task leader (Het PON & Telos) informed partners over the course of several general meetings about the content and structure of the task. Het PON & Telos also presented what input was necessary to be able to report on activities relating to the task and while some information was already available, the partners also had to work on specific sections which were then incorporated and presented by the task leader.

All participating partners received an Excel template in which they were able to track of their internal and external capacity building activities. Questions in the Excel were sometimes quantitative in nature, for example: “what was the male/female distribution within the project partners who worked on the EnergyMeasures project?”. Other questions were more qualitative, *e.g.*, “did you organise any internal training and/or upskilling during WP2?”; “What kind of training?”; “Who were taking part of the training?”; “What was the focus on the training?”; “What materials were used?”; “Who gave the training?”, *etc.* Het PON & Telos then collected the completed templates and incorporated them into section 2 *Internal Capacity Building* and section 3 *External Capacity Building*.

The research question concerning the impact this project has had on policy innovations to alleviate energy poverty has also been addressed through the joint input of the partners. Partners were asked to identify examples in which they have sought to positively impact the energy poverty policy context in their respective countries. Section 4, which deals with these policy innovations summarises the results from D3.1 and D3.2, and discusses the potential within a specific policy context in more detail.

1.5 Reading Guide

In sections 2 and 3, capacity building activities are discussed. These sections aim to address the question as to what extent the project has contributed to knowledge about alleviating energy poverty. Section 4 then, discusses which policy innovations emerged from that knowledge. In conclusion, section 5 examines to what extent those actions contributed to alleviating energy poverty in the participating countries.

2 Internal capacity building

In this section, the internal capacity building of participating partners is discussed. This will include the development of knowledge and skills of the employees working in the project. In section 2.2, we discuss the activities that were undertaken to bring the knowledge level of employees up to standard across the participating countries. In section 2.3, the internal capacity building within the consortium is discussed. We conclude with some thoughts on how this internal capacity building has helped alleviate energy poverty (see section 2.4). However, before we delve deeper into the internal capacity building numbers, let us first look at some general numbers that have been important for the project.

2.1 General figures on EnergyMeasures

2.1.1 Participating countries and partners

The EnergyMeasures H2020 Coordination and support action (CSA) project consortium consisted of twelve partners from eight European countries, with household engagements taking place in seven of the eight countries. The eighth country of the consortium, Austria with Oikoplus as partner, was responsible for the coordinating the communication and dissemination effort associated with the project and therefore did not partake in the household engagement activities in WP2.

Table 1 Table highlighting the gender breakdown of staff members that contributed to the project.

Country	Partner	Females	Males	Total
Ireland	University College Cork – National University of Ireland, Cork	6	2	8
Ireland	Energy Action CLG	2	2	4
Netherlands	DuneWorks BV	1	1	2
Netherlands	Het PON & Telos	2	1	3
Netherlands	Gemeente Eindhoven	1		1
Belgium	APB Kamp C	1	1	2
Belgium	SAAMO Provincie Antwerpen vzw	2		2
Poland	Stowarzyszenie Gmin Polska Sieć Energie Cités	7	4	11
North Macedonia	Residential Building Management Company Habidom DOOEL		2	2
Bulgaria	Association Municipal Energy Efficiency Network EcoEnergy	3	6	9
United Kingdom	Tighean Innse Gall	2	1	3
Austria	Oikoplus	4	4	8
Total of people who worked on the project		31	24	55

2.1.2 Duration and makeup of household engagement activities

The project had initially been planned to last for 36 months. However, given the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic and the knock-on effects – compounded by shifting policy landscapes in some of the participating countries – necessitated a grant amendment to restructure the project and extend its duration by six months until 29 February 2024. The additional time afforded by the extension did in some measure help to mitigate the pressures on the project arising from the pandemic, but of course it could not fully rectify matters. The pandemic significantly inhibited household recruitment and engagement. During the first half of the project this was directly due to social and travel restrictions put in place by governments to address the health crisis. Subsequently, it was an indirect impact as householders remained extremely wary of bringing people into their homes. The result was that although recruitment targets were met, householders joined the project far later than planned and consequently participated in the project for less time than originally envisaged. Table 2 below presents an overview of the scale of engagement activities in each participating country. For a more in-depth presentation of the household engagements for EnergyMeasures see D2.4 Periodic update #2 on engagement of energy poor for behaviour change.

Table 2 Household recruitment compared to targets per country.

	Belgium	Bulgaria	Ireland ^{2,3}	Netherlands	North Macedonia ³	Poland	UK	Overall
Target	500	600	600	400	650	400	500	3,650
Participants recruited	598	723	603	403	620	450	511	3,908
Surplus (Deficit)	120	123	3	3	(30)	50	11	258

2.2 Internal capacity building within the participating countries

2.2.1 Belgium

In Belgium, Kamp C (Centre for Sustainability and Innovation in Construction) and SAAMO (social work in eight provinces in Flanders) worked together, forming what was referred to as the ‘Belgian cluster’. Internal capacity building in this cluster focused mainly on training and familiarising new colleagues on the nuances of working with the target households, along with contextual factors that underline experiences in Belgium. The work associated with introducing new colleagues to the EnergyMeasures project, including explaining the content and structure of the project, was undertaken by more senior in Kamp C and Saamo. While they did not develop or apply specific training material for this capacity building involved *ad hoc* mentoring in combination with new colleagues directed to familiarise themselves with the project’s Description of Action (DoA) and from anonymised insights gleaned from questionnaires used in the household engagement.

² Following the termination of Energy Action CLG, the recruitment target for Ireland was reduced by 50 households (to provide flexibility given the inevitable disruption to activities), with a corresponding increase for North Macedonia. While achieving this full increase did prove not possible in the time available in North Macedonia, the numbers were made up elsewhere in the consortium.

³ It should be noted that following Energy Action’s termination, the staff member responsible for engagement continued working (under PNEC) and managed to achieve 83% of the original Dublin target despite losing much of the local support team available to him during the first half of the project.

2.2.2 Bulgaria

EcoEnergy employees and EnEffect experts participated in numerous working meetings prior to the household engagement activities, and they engaged (both online and at their office) in specific internal training with staff during the implementation of the project. Training and information seminars organised through peer initiatives were generally attended by most employees to gain knowledge and share useful insights and tips with colleagues. These training events and meetings covered the topics of energy efficiency measures, energy poverty, building renovation, construction skills, municipal energy management, financial instruments, *etc.* Usually, technical trainings were provided by experienced engineers. The materials used for the training have been developed in the context of projects coordinated by EnEffect or in which EnEffect or EcoEnergy are partners and are kept on file with the intention that lessons learned from EnergyMeasures will inform future projects within both organisations.

2.2.3 Ireland

Numerous internal training events were organised in Ireland, mainly to train junior staff members. Given its university context, junior staff are primarily research assistant, doctoral students, and postdoctoral researchers and as such benefit from the university's Professional Development Plans (PDPs) and mentorship programmes. Senior staff actively supported junior staff with training comprising of a multi-layered approach to how to deal effectively with households (including the interpersonal 'soft skills' such as entering a household, putting people at ease, how to effectively conduct interviews, reflexively understanding one's own beliefs, judgments, and practices during the engagement process, *etc.*). Training also included upgrading data management (IT) skills and organisational trainings. The IT training involved computers skills of individual staff members; engagement training sessions including the use of in-house training space and equipment and was given by senior staff members.

2.2.4 North Macedonia

In North Macedonia, the internal capacity building consisted mainly of training on how to conduct an effective interview for those colleagues engaging directly with the participating households. The focus was not only on conducting an interview, but also on how a household could be approached and recruited for the EnergyMeasures project. This involved internal training given by a senior employee of Habidom, the North Macedonian partner in the project. The training material consisted of material prepared by the project.

2.2.5 Poland

As part of its internal training programme, senior PNEC staff organised a workshop for energy advisors and junior staff in Poland in February 2022. The first part of this workshop focused on knowledge about good energy practices and behaviour, local subsidies, and low-cost practices in households. The second part included communication and improving skills for effective contact and communication with citizens. The workshop aimed to understand the multi-dimensional nature of energy poverty and its implications for households. It also involved understanding current policy frameworks for alleviating energy poverty and finding the right solutions and options for households. During the workshop, effective strategies were developed and discussed to involve households in the implementation of good energy habits. These workshops used materials developed by PNEC, the Polish partner in the consortium, and by the Municipality of Bielsko-Biala. Materials from other government websites have also been used.

2.2.6 The Netherlands

In December and January of 2021 and 2022, four training courses were provided to the three energy advisers employed by the Municipality of Eindhoven and who contributed to EnergyMeasures effort in Eindhoven. The focus of the training differed per session. The first session mainly involved explaining the EnergyMeasures project. The subsequent sessions were about how resilience works in people, safety awareness during home visits, expectation management, and the importance of ventilation and good indoor air quality. These training courses were provided by two of the three Dutch partners, Duneworks and Het PON & Telos (referred within the consortium as the 'Dutch cluster'). The Dutch partners worked closely with Energiebox, an organisation that provides energy advice to households and distributes a box with easy energy-saving measures to households and whose advisers referred households eligible for participation in the EnergyMeasures project. In September 2022, the energy advisers of Energiebox attended a peer-to-peer workshop with the central theme '*How to have the right conversation with a household?*'. This peer-to-peer workshop was given by Het PON & Telos, who also developed the materials for this. In developing the knowledge base of Energiebox employees and junior members of staff in the Dutch cluster, responsible staff members were able to build work together more seamlessly towards realising the project goals in the Netherlands.

2.2.7 United Kingdom

In Scotland UK, internal capacity building included training to better inform the energy advisers who would carry out the home visits. The focus of the training included being alert to the signals of energy poverty during home visits. The training not only consisted of a theoretical part, but joint visits with senior staff were made to households to learn how a home visit can work in practice. The training was initially provided by the project manager. In later phases of the training, the teammates watched each other's home visits and learning was more a peer-to-peer construction.

2.3 Internal capacity building within the consortium

Throughout the project, there were regular events (online and in-person) when partners met and worked together on the capacity building within the project.

In addition to the internal capacity building of junior staff members, UCC organised capacity building workshops to coincide with the activities of the bi-annual general assembly meetings. This work was complemented by a focused capacity building workshop that took place in December 2021 in Dublin. This two-day workshop was a hybrid meeting that could be attended both in-person and online. The aim of the second day of the meeting was to exchange best practices regarding approaching vulnerable households that could be affected by energy poverty. In addition, the workshops involved exchanging practices on data collection and processing.

In May/June 2022, during the general meeting in Eindhoven several workshops on internal capacity building were integrated into the programme. These workshops had different areas of focus, along the lines of the different work packages. The workshop topics included household recruitment and engagement, on quantifying impact and on communication (which conferences to attend, or which publications to work on).

These meetings and their associated workshops offered members of the consortium (particularly new members of staff within the partner organisations) the opportunity to exchange knowledge and tips in order to jointly achieve a higher level of knowledge and improve the level of service to the participating households.

2.4 Contribution to alleviating energy poverty

The seven countries of the consortium actively engaged in peer related knowledge transfer, including guiding other (sometimes junior) employees within the EnergyMeasures project and teaching skills such as interviewing. It also involved building topical knowledge, such as how to properly ventilate and the installation of energy-saving products within the different cohorts participating in the project. Lastly, it involved knowledge building around social topics such as the impact of energy poverty on people's lives.

The partners indicated that by offering a workshop or training, they felt they were bringing their employees to the right level of knowledge to carry out this project (often involving visiting households). In North Macedonia, for example, energy advisers working for the MK partner were able to work independently in households after the training. In the United Kingdom, the team had a better understanding of the different housing types, heating and hot water systems, and the use of appliances in the homes after their training. In Belgium internal capacity building helped to refine the household recruitment strategy. This information informed other aspects of the work programme undertaken by consortium partners beyond EnergyMeasures. It also helped partners to define the target groups and specify the goals to be achieved.

3 External capacity building

As mentioned in the introduction, external capacity building is divided into three parts: external capacity building among professionals outside of the partner organisations, among households, and within the contexts of energy poverty policy. The latter form of external capacity building is central to section 4. In this section we focus on the first two forms of capacity building. In section 3.2 we describe per country what activities have been undertaken to build the knowledge and skills of both professionals and households. In section 3.3 we look at how external capacity building among professionals and households has contributed to alleviating energy poverty.

The behavioural component of households is one of the key aspects of the EnergyMeasures project. Structural, not incidental energy savings are integral to reducing both consumption and energy poverty and contain a behavioural aspect. Therefore, partners also kept track of how many households used energy more consciously after intervention. How many households have changed their energy behaviour? What did they mainly do? And how structural have the adjustments in their behaviour been? The quantitative component of this project is part of WP4.2, but to provide some context, there is a brief summary included as section 3.1.

3.1 General figures on behaviour change

As outlined in **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.** below, EnergyMeasures reached some 10,778 people directly through participation of their household in the project and indirectly through other engagements. . All these participants received information on how to change their energy behaviours and

practices. For a breakdown of the different types of behaviour change advice received by participants in the seven focal countries, along with the most useful advice as indicated by participants see *D4.4 Report on success of behaviour change initiatives amongst energy poor households*. We estimate that 95% of these people to change (at least some of) their energy related behaviours as a result⁴, *i.e.* c. 10,239 people (compared to a target of 10,000 people).

Table 3 Total number of people reached by the project.

Country	# Households	Average # residents	# participants reached	# Others reached
Belgium	598	2.58	1,543	0
Bulgaria	723	1.83	1,323	220 ⁵
Ireland	603	2.45	1,480	695 ⁶
Poland	450	2.24	1,008	0
North Macedonia	620	3.10	1,992	0
Scotland, UK	511	1.92	981	659 ⁷
Netherlands	403	2.35	948	0
Sub-total	3,908		9,205 (a)	878 (b)
			Total reached (a + b)	10,778

3.2 External capacity building within the participating countries.

Partners in all countries were involved in external capacity building. In the following paragraphs, the nature of the contribution in each participating country is discussed.

3.2.1 Belgium

External capacity building among professionals

If we look at the external capacity building among professionals in Belgium, we see that the Flemish partners have organised various knowledge-building activities during the EnergyMeasures project. These include online webinars about energy poverty among social workers, but also face-to-face meetings for employees of the Municipality of Turnhout and for the housing association of this municipality. The purpose of these meetings was to advise local authorities on the issue of energy poverty and how they can support residents. In addition, information was provided about the energy crisis. Those meetings resulted in more cooperation

⁴ Given the feedback from participants on behavior change (see D4.4), the motivation of those attending energy clinics, and the context of the external driver of the energy crisis we posit that this is a reasonable estimate.

⁵ An additional 120 households (c. 220 residents) were engaged in Bulgaria, while they did not formally participate in the project, they were provided with advice and guidance on energy issues.

⁶ 695 additional participants (additional to those who participated) were reached through a series of energy clinics and other events (organised *e.g.*, through active retirement networks and Health Service Executive).

⁷ TIG engaged an additional 343 households (659 residents) who were deemed not eligible to participate as they did not match all the criteria. However, they were still provided with energy advice and referred on to the appropriate state services. These residents would not have been provide with such support had it not been for EnergyMeasures project.

between stakeholders and a more joint approach to both energy poverty and the energy crisis (caused by the war in Ukraine and associated uncertainty about energy continuity).

In addition, collaboration has been sought with students from the Thomas More University of Applied Sciences and with various departments of the Energie Snoeiers (an organisation that provides energy advice to energy-poor households). In the context of T6.3, an international exchange took place between Flemish and Dutch energy advisers. The energy advisers used a dialogue framework to work on a number of questions that arise in both countries. The purpose of this meeting was to exchange knowledge and tips and practices about how the work as an energy adviser can best be carried out. [Table 4](#) presents the key training workshops organised in Belgium.

Table 4 Training workshops organised by the Belgium cluster

Date	15-12-2023
Location	Gent
Organisations represented	a very wide range of organizations and individuals committed to a socially just energy transition
Number of attendees	26 in workshop
Brief description of workshop	“Festival of equality” - workshop: the role of people in energy poverty in the energy transition - how do we include everyone?
Date	12-12-2023
Location	Geel and Turnhout
Organisations represented	Poverty-organisations ‘Alarm’ and ‘T ANTWOORD’
Number of participants	10 + 8
Brief description of training	Use of digital energy meter (better follow-up of energy savings)
Date	19-10-2023
Location	Antwerp
Organisations represented	Energy scan companies (social employment) from all over Flanders
Number of participants	120 in total, over 2 workshops (26 + 24)
Brief description of training	The “day of the energy savers” with 2 capacity building workshops with a focus on the effects and desires of material to use small measures during visits. We take a closer look at the savings package, zoom in on some of the materials, see how they can be optimally used and what effect they have on energy consumption. We also dwell on new materials and techniques, taking inspiration from foreign examples and listening to some experienced Energy Savers.
Date	09-06-2023
Location	Turnhout
Organisations represented	CAW De Kempen Team Housing – Welzijnsonthaal Turnhout – OCMW Turnhout Team Housing - Woonboog (social housing company)
Number of participants	31

Brief description of training	The federal government has extended the social tariff during the energy crisis but abolished the measure from July 1, 23. 500.000 families are affected. What can the welfare sector do to cushion the impact?
Date	16-05-2023
Location	Turnhout
Organisations represented	LIGO – primary education center
Number of participants	10 + 21 (over two sessions)
Brief description of training	Training session as part of the integration program: How to save energy? - practical tips. Also, how to find a cheap energy supplier; How to read an energy bill; and How to use the home meter?
Date	26-01-2023
Location	Turnhout
Organisations represented	Social Welfare Turnhout – City of Turnhout
Number of participants	7
Brief description of training	Training session for single mothers in a vulnerable situation (MYRIAM-project): how to save energy? - practical tips - how to find a cheap energy supplier? - how to read an energy bill? How to use the home meter?
Date	21-01-2023
Location	Mechelen
Organisations represented	Beweging.net stakeholder meeting
Number of participants	25
Brief description of training	What is energy poverty? How can we tackle it? From small measures to structural interventions and innovative projects.

External capacity building among households

When it comes to external capacity building among households, the community development organisation SAAMO in particular developed many activities. Among their activities we find nine presentations held in person at various organisations. This includes organisations that are committed to combatting poverty, education centres, housing associations and community centres. In addition, four neighbourhood action days were held and more than 400 brochures about the sale of energy contracts were distributed through bike tours. Finally, SAAMO has held drop-in moments at the office to help people with their energy bills.

The topics of these meetings were: all-round energy-saving tips, use of the Woonmeter (Residential meter – a tool for better ventilation and heating), engagement for the EnergyMeasures project, awareness for door-to-door energy contract sellers, and the benefits of using radiator fans (if possible).

3.2.2 Bulgaria

External capacity building among professionals

In Bulgaria, the organised knowledge sessions were not so much aimed at providing information about energy poverty, but more at formulating clear policies and measures to overcome energy poverty in Bulgaria.

In addition, two meetings focused on the energy-efficient renovation of the housing stock. The knowledge sharing is therefore about the possibilities of renovation as an instrument to combat energy poverty. By making this topic the focus of the knowledge sharing, the needs there for further capacity building among stakeholders and for technical assistance from municipalities became clearer.

EcoEnergy/Eneffect set things in motion with the knowledge sessions. For example, there has been active lobbying for the establishment of a definition of energy poverty. In addition, this partner has succeeded in involving a professional community on the topic of energy poverty and the cross-sectoral dimension of this topic. Finally, partnerships have been established with organisations that also work in the field of energy and climate.

Participants in the knowledge sessions organised by EcoEnergy/Eneffect came from national and local governments, businesses, NGOs, academia and professional associations. *Table 5* presents the key training workshops organised in Bulgaria.

Table 5 Training workshops organised in Bulgaria

Date	08-07-2022
Location	Gabrovo
Organisations represented	Gabrovo Municipality, EnEffect, HOAs
Number of participants	13
Brief description of training	Seminar for building managers and HOAs about building renovation, EE measures, key moments for application to the National EE renovation of MFABs programme.
Date	03-06-2022
Location	Burgas
Organisations represented	Burgas Municipality, EnEffect, HOAs
Number of participants	20
Brief description of training	The training seminar was aimed at building managers and homeowners on the topic of building renovations in light of the National EE renovation of MFABs programme, outlining important moments and technical information that need to be taken into consideration when applying.
Date	12-4-2022
Location	Gabrovo municipality
Organisations represented	EnEffect, Gabrovo municipality,
Number of participants	60
Brief description of training	Apartment owners in residential buildings were trained on the benefits of building renovation. Topics included: energy audits, building renovation, real-time monitoring results of individual apartments.
Date	15-2-2022
Location	Gabrovo

Organisations represented	EnEffect, Gabrovo municipality
Number of participants	20
Brief description of training	Training for municipal experts on the topic of energy efficiency, municipal energy management, citizens' engagement, awareness raising.
Date	22-11-2021
Location	Gabrovo
Organisations represented	EnEffect, Gabrovo municipality
Number of participants	13
Brief description of training	A training for HOAs and building owners on the basic principles of energy efficiency, energy management, behavior change practices, low-investment measures to save energy.
Date	23-09-2021
Location	Smolyan, Bulgaria
Organisations represented	EnEffect, EcoEnergy, BACIW, BCC, HOAs, Smolyan municipality
Number of participants	15
Brief description of training	Homeowners and building managers training session organized within the nZEB Days – public events, featuring roundtable discussions with policymakers, building sector professionals, manufacturers, academia, local authorities, businesses, product fair, training seminars for engineers and architects, games for kids, part of a series supported by the H2020 project nZEB Roadshow, ran by EnEffect.
Date	December 2020
Location	Online
Organisations represented	The training was conducted by experts from EnEffect, and officially supported by Sofia University, Sofia Municipality, Bulgarian Construction Chamber and Municipal Energy Efficiency Network EcoEnergy.
Number of participants	140
Brief description of training	An online training course for representatives of homeowners' associations and local authorities was designed to stimulate the public participation in the renovation policies, consisting of 7 consecutive 1,5-hour sessions. The training course was developed and conducted by EnEffect, attracting more than 140 registered participants and broad exposure in the social networks.

External capacity building among households

To stimulate public participation in renovation policy, an online training for representatives of owners' associations and local authorities has been designed, consisting of 7 consecutive sessions of 1.5 hours. The training was developed and given by EnEffect, attracted more than 140 registered participants and was

widely shared on social networks. The training series was officially supported by Sofia University, Sofia Municipality, Bulgarian Construction Chamber and municipal energy efficiency network EcoEnergy.

During these seven knowledge-sharing sessions, technical information, energy saving tips, and behavioural advice were provided to the participating households. In addition, a number of major awareness events were designed with the aim of reaching citizens, informing and involving them about the options available to support the energy-efficient renovation of buildings. These energy-efficient renovations then served as a means to also alleviate the living conditions of energy-poor households.

The external capacity building among households made it possible to inform residents about small affordable housing improvements to prevent mould, moisture retention, and heat reduction. In addition, information was provided on the financial supports available for the renovation of buildings, procurement procedures, establishment of homeowner's associations and application to various national support programs.

If we look at the behaviour of the households involved, it is noteworthy that they characterise the common experience of those living energy poverty who continually monitor their own energy consumption and energy bills more carefully than the rest of the population with knock-on impacts on other decision-making within the household.

3.2.3 Ireland

External capacity building among professionals

In Ireland the project team held a business modelling workshop for several delegates from NGOs and charities in January 2023. During this business modelling workshop, participants discussed questions such as: *How do we address the structural and physical conditions of energy poverty? How is your organisation working to meet the challenge of energy poverty and what are the key challenges you face implementing it?* By allowing professionals from different angles to discuss this with each other and share experiences knowledge on how to best tackle energy poverty was further spread. It was striking that the NGOs have diverse capacities and that they have built up different institutional knowledge on the subject of energy poverty.

In addition to this knowledge exchange, the meeting was also used to introduce the EnergyMeasures project to NGOs and government agencies charged with tackling energy poverty. A result of this external capacity building was that the meeting created new relationships between the participants present. Furthermore, it showed that existing organisations really want to work together. The NGOs and charities in attendance showed a keen interest in exploring how they could pool resources to maximise their impact by providing services to energy vulnerable households. [Table 6](#) presents the key training workshops organised in Ireland.

Table 6 Training workshops organised in Ireland

Date	29-11-2022
Location	Online
Organisations represented	Energy Action Local Community Development Company
Number of participants	16

Brief description of training	60-minute training session delivered by C. Roarty.
	21-11-2022
Location	Online
Organisations represented	Energy Action, Robert Emmet Community Development Company
Number of participants	16
Brief description of training	90-minute training session
Date	14-11-2022
Location	Online
Organisations represented	Energy Action, Robert Emmet Community Development Company
Number of participants	14
Brief description of training	90-minute training session
Date	19-10-2022
Location	Nationwide
Organisations represented	Energy Action, ALONE
Number of participants	36
Brief description of training	This half day training session was delivered to all ALONE staff nationwide. ALONE has 7 different regions throughout the country and their training officers then delivered this training to their own staff to help older people during the energy crisis.
Date	19-11-2021
Location	Online
Organisations represented	Energy Action, MABS
Number of participants	45
Brief description of training	This half day training session was delivered to all MABS Training offices online.
Date	05-10-2021
Location	EA offices, Dublin
Organisations represented	Energy Action
Number of participants	7
Brief description of training	Energy Advice Training to EA staff

External capacity building among households

If we look at external capacity building around households, we see that the Irish partners have been very active over the course of the project. UCC, for example, has run numerous energy clinics aimed at community and active retirement groups in the Cork area. These sessions were undertaken with the aim of achieving

multiple goals, resulting in addition to knowledge transfer the opportunity was also taken to recruit households for the project at these meetings with among those attending or from the wider networks of the attendees.

Households received a variety of information about behavioural and organisational changes they could make to improve the energy efficiency of their homes. These included: only boiling as much water as necessary in the kettle, installing draught excluders to seal gaps around windows and doors, using dryer balls to speed up drying times in the tumble dryer, *etc.*

Larger energy events have also been held in the Cork region. The UCC team presented pop-up style energy clinics, which were mainly used as recruitment opportunities. The project staff also organised a personal recruitment campaign in which direct contact was made with residents where they talked about the project and the energy-saving measures.

Given the variation in housing stock in Ireland, the energy saving measures that were most common for individuals varied. However, particular interest was shown in reducing energy through insulation, identifying 'vampire devices', *etc.* The most applied actions were related to the use and installation of energy measures provided to households, including the installation of radiator foil, draught excluders, and moisture absorbers.

Households implemented several behavioural changes after becoming more aware of how to save energy and in turn reduce bills. We see that residents became more aware of a number of actions. For example, participants indicated they now only start the laundry when a full washing machine could be run. Households also became increasingly aware of the benefits of turning down/off radiators in unused rooms, and closing the curtains at night to keep heat from escaping through glass windows. By informing households on how behavioural changes improve the energy saving potential associated with the low-cost materials they receive, they can take certain aspects of their energy savings into their own hands.

3.2.4 North-Macedonia

External capacity building among professionals

Habidom, the North Macedonian partner, held a workshop and preparatory interviews in the context of external capacity building. Based on these interviews, a workshop was developed among policymakers. This workshop took place in September 2023 in Skopje and was part of effort linked to T3.2, which is discussed in the next section.

Table 7 Training workshops organised in North Macedonia

Date	02-03-2023
Location	Habidom
Organisations represented	Makoteks Milenium
Number of participants	4
Brief description of training	Short explanation of the project and its goals. The 620 households were introduced to the people from Makoteks Milenium since they were doing the interviews and implement the gifts. Afterwards second visit was made in order to see if there is improvement.

External capacity building among households

In North Macedonia, no separate meetings have been organised for households in energy poverty. However, 620 households have been recruited for the project, with participants actively involved receiving energy-saving measures and appropriate advice.

3.2.5 Poland

External capacity building among professionals

In Poland, external capacity building among professionals consisted of several components, which took place at different times. For example, two webinars were held with a one-year interval, both on the topic of ‘Technical assistance to tackle energy poverty’. The approximately 100 participants came from the local administration, social organisations, NGOs, and regional government. In addition, monthly lunch meetings were held in Poland starting November 2022 on themes related to energy poverty. Themes included: ‘The importance of indicators in local energy poverty assessment’, ‘How to involve different stakeholder groups in energy poverty efforts?’ and ‘Tackling energy poverty through behaviour change’. The participants in these lunch meetings were, amongst others, energy experts, stakeholders, and representatives of municipalities.

Two national meetings were held in May 2022 and May 2023, at which the Polish EnergyMeasures partner contributed. The focus of this contribution was on explaining the project and drawing on research that supports the importance of energy advice. The effect of this meeting was to broaden knowledge about energy transition, identify pathways to reduce energy poverty, and activate residents by giving them new information and show examples of successful measures and solutions.

Finally, an International Annual Conference on Energy Poverty was held in Warsaw in the fall of 2023. The aim of this was to investigate how to arrive at an effective structural and long-term policy to combat and prevent energy poverty. [Table 8](#) presents the key training workshops organised in Poland.

Table 8 Training workshops organised in Poland

Date	16-10-2023
Location	online
Organisations represented	PNEC
Number of participants	10
Brief description of training	Training on energy poverty in Zamość: The training covered topics such as best practices for engaging vulnerable residents (include EnergyMeasures project) and those affected by energy poverty crises, available sources of financing, and included a workshop on the long-term strategy for combating energy poverty in the Zamość Area.
Date	22 – 26-05-2023
Location	Bielsko-Biała
Organisations represented	PNEC

Number of participants	24
Brief description of training	The visit was aimed at exchanging experiences, sharing ideas and best practices of the CoM Signatories in energy efficiency, sustainable energy development and adaptation to climate change policy as well as at getting to know local development initiatives and strengthening cooperation. EnergyMeasures project and its activities was presented to guests from East European countries.
Date	23.03.2023
Location	Zamość
Organisations represented	PNEC
Number of participants	12
Brief description of training	Training on energy poverty in Zamość: The workshop addressed Energy Poverty in Europe & Poland, covering definitions, causes, consequences, as well as assessing and countering energy poverty at the local level with a focus on the situation in Zamość. During the workshop, the discussion centred on diagnosing energy poverty in Zamość and implementing awareness-raising campaign projects for vulnerable households.
Date	02-2022
Location	Bielsko-Biała
Organisations represented	PNEC
Number of participants	6
Brief description of training	Energy Advisors Training: The subject of the training was the sustainable lifestyle habits in the aspect of energy for households, local subsidies and technical aspects on energy related topics. It explained the importance of EnergyMeasures programme, included the explanation of the "Energia na miarę" Programme terms (consulted with the lawyer).

External capacity building among households

To inform residents of Bielsko-Biala about the EnergyMeasures project, various information sessions were held in key locations, with different target groups. The topic of the knowledge sessions focused on sustainable lifestyle habits in the topic of energy use in households. During these short meetings, it was possible to participate in the project (recruitment in part explaining the program conditions "Energia na miarę" – tailor made energy). The focus was on filling the gap in people's knowledge and demonstrating the benefits of participating in the program. About 50 residents participated in the information sessions. In addition, attention was paid to the project and ways to save energy in Bielsko-Biala in the local media and on social media (e.g., Facebook). A newsletter was regularly sent to the participants in the project with information about how to save energy.

Due to the knowledge building in Poland, households have gained more insight in their energy consumption. Hence, they are now able to identify what they can easily adjust themselves to save (some) energy. People

have also gained more knowledge about local subsidy programs and, partly thanks to their participation in EnergyMeasures, have submitted applications to avail of those subsidies.

3.2.6 The Netherlands

External capacity building among professionals

A number of activities have taken place in the Netherlands that can be grouped under the heading ‘external capacity building among professionals’. In the context of work package 3, T3.1 ‘*Innovative governance initiatives to address structural causes of energy poverty*’, three business modelling workshops were held within the consortium, one of which took place in the Netherlands. Those present were first offered a range of presentations about new business models at Dutch energy cooperatives, after which they discussed how a sustainably generated income can more easily benefit projects that combat energy poverty. Ten stakeholders participated in this business modelling workshop. In addition to this business modelling workshop, three webinars were held on the topic of energy poverty, two of which were organised together with the Horizon2020 sister project ENPOR.⁸

In September 2023, the Dutch partners held a resilience dialogue in the context of the dissemination strategy as formulated in T6.3, during which more than 40 professionals engaged in structured discussions on a range of topics related to energy poverty. These topics were: *How do we ensure that saving energy becomes an important topic for everyone? How can we better anchor a long-term approach to energy poverty in policy terms? How can we use the proceeds of solar and wind energy to tackle energy poverty?*

These capacity building activities among professionals taught the Dutch project team that energy poverty is considered an important issue and that many people are professionally involved in it. However, we also see that the Dutch government is still pursuing little policy to structurally reduce energy poverty. The current policy landscape seems to be mainly focused on applying small energy-saving measures, energy ‘coaching’, and having municipalities distribute an energy allowance to households to compensate them for their energy bills. That allowance discontinued as of Jan-2024, leaving vulnerable households with (renewed) problems.

Table 9 Training workshops organised in the Netherlands

Date	Dec. 21 – Jan 22
Location	Eindhoven at the Municipality
Organisations represented	Duneworks, Municipality of Eindhoven, Het PON & Telos
Number of participants	3
Brief description of training	This involved four internal training courses for the hired energy advisers who were starting the household engagement. We had four training mornings to properly explain the EM project to them and prepare them for the home visits. Topics that were discussed: how do you enter a household, how do you start talking about energy poverty, how do you inspire people's trust, safety, the importance of good information, ventilate the home for a healthy indoor climate, working with the Earn-E (a device that tracks real-time energy consumption).

⁸ ENPOR was focused on the issue of reducing energy poverty in the private rental sector. <https://enpor.eu/>.

External capacity building among households

Over the course of the EnergyMeasures project, various activities took place in Eindhoven to inform residents about energy poverty, energy consumption, and energy savings. First of all, the energy advisers actively provided information on behalf of the project during the ‘Groene Wijk Week’ (Green Neighbourhood Week). This week was intended for anyone interested in living more sustainably. It is estimated that approximately 100 people have been reached. Secondly, six presentations were given during the themed meetings on ‘Het leven wordt duurder’ (Life is becoming more expensive). These meetings were mainly intended for elderly people who have little to spend. A total of approximately 300 people attended the meetings. Thirdly, every Tuesday, the energy advisers of the Municipality of Eindhoven staff the energy information point in the Eindhoven library. Residents can go there with all their questions relating to energy, such as energy surcharges, sustainability, subsidies, savings, and possible support from the municipality. Often three to four people per week can be helped with their questions.

Finally, in September 2022, nine primary schools participated in the ‘Energy Race’, a project in which they received a guest lesson on energy saving after which they introduced what they had learned to their own families. The 411 participating students ultimately distributed 142 energy boxes to their family members; 62% of the distributed energy boxes ended up in postal code areas known to have substantive numbers of households dealing with energy poverty.

3.2.7 United Kingdom

External capacity building among professionals

A number of external capacity meetings took place in the Outer Hebrides during the project. Firstly, a meeting was held in November 2021 with the team from Social Security Scotland, an organisation that helps residents of Scotland pay social security benefits, resulting in several exchanges of information between both organisations. One of these exchanges included learning about the latest types of social benefits available, so that the project team could point this out to households during their home visits. At the same time, the employees of Tighean Innse Gall (TIG) highlighted the EnergyMeasures project to households. This information exchange made it easier to aid households and to receive direct household referrals for this project from Social Security Scotland.

A second capacity building activity took place when the Just Transition Commission held a meeting in the Outer Hebrides. The Just Transition Commission conducts independent research into justice within climate actions in Scotland. At this meeting, TIG presented the EnergyMeasures project and TIG employees gained knowledge about the work of the Just Transitions Commission.

Table 10 Training workshops organised in the United Kingdom (Scotland)

Date	02-12-2022
Location	Triumpanhead over 60's Club, Aird Community Centre, Point, Isle of Lewis
Organisations represented	Community representatives
Number of participants	29
Brief description of training	This was a training session for small community groups and individuals in a distinct geographical area of the Isle of Lewis. Membership of the over 60's

	<p>group included multiple members of wider community organisations in the islands. This follows the ‘wearing many hats’ rule, which is one person might attend as an individual, but in other circumstances is involved with different community groups. Strategically this is important to understand, as it forms a key mechanism to secure wider outreach in a community where individuals are involved in many things on a community basis.</p> <p>The training outline what the project was, how it could help people and the way to become involved in it. 22 people present joined the project at the session, which in itself was a success (nearly 5% of total numbers). However, a spike in recruitment was noted immediately afterwards through word of mouth and sharing information from the session.</p>
Date	
Location	Breasclete Community Centre, Carloway, Isle of Lewis.
Organisations represented	Carloway Estate Trust, Callanish Trust, Carloway Community Association
Number of participants	20
Brief description of training	This was a session designed to inform community organisations and individuals about the project. This was also to take up referrals and signups for the project at the event. We trained the groups on what the project was, how it would benefit citizens in the geographical areas of the participants remits, and how to refer energy poor households.
Date	24-11-2021
Location	Online: Teams meeting
Organisations represented	Social Security Scotland
Number of participants	6
Brief description of training	EnergyMeasures team briefed Social Security Scotland (SSS) managers and staff on the aims of our project and how it could help claimants of Scottish entitlements. We established early on that nearly all their clients would be fuel poor, that EnergyMeasures support would be invaluable to them, and therefore would benefit from being referred to us. We demonstrated the pathways for SSS staff to refer their client base, identified potential stumbling blocks (data protection) and solutions to overcome them (materials distributed by SSS officers) and agreed to partner to benefit households in the islands.

External capacity building among households

TIG organised 13 public events to increase the profile of the project. These included online events during the pandemic, as well as public talks and a partnership with the Post Office, where TIG staff had consultation sessions in local post offices. Many attendees were unaware of the project, nor of the types of support available from local, devolved Scottish government or even in Britain.

TIG sought collaboration with other parties at the events and in this way ‘piggybacked’ on the public events of others. These include, for example, the municipal library service, where TIG employees attended pop-up

climate events. In addition, presentations were given at community events such as an over-60s club, summer festivals, and coffee mornings.

Almost all households used LED lighting. Common behavioural changes include changes in the use of water and energy consumption. Households have mainly gained knowledge about using their heating systems effectively, cooking more efficiently, and reducing hot water consumption by taking shorter showers and not heating the hot water tanks for an unnecessarily long time.

3.3 Contribution to alleviating energy poverty

Working on external capacity building among both professionals and households has proven to be important for the EnergyMeasures project. Capacity building among households has been part and parcel of the household engagements that were central to the EnergyMeasures project. In several partner countries, additional activities or interventions have been conducted to reach households. External capacity building has also been important for the professionals and professional organisations with which partners have started working. Firstly, in this way they could bring the EnergyMeasures project to the attention of others and perhaps find more households that were eligible to participate. On the other hand, during the period that the EnergyMeasures project was running, a lot was also learned about all kinds of matters related to reducing energy poverty. Considering ways in which households experience energy poverty can be better understood as a result, but also issues such as new business models that can be financially beneficial for these households, or ways in which local energy policy has been influenced can also be ascertained (see also section 4). It is estimated that more than 10,750 people have been engaged by the EnergyMeasures project. These people have all gained more knowledge in at least one of the many aspects to energy poverty, energy saving behaviours and/or energy poverty policy. These are knowledge and capabilities that they might not have acquired without this project.

4 Monitoring of structural initiatives

In the previous sections we discussed the internal and external capacity building initiated by the EnergyMeasures project. Earlier, in the introduction, we described a third form of capacity building (*i.e.*, institutional capacity building) referring to the process of enhancing the effectiveness of the institutional context (*i.e.*, policies, regulations, and the distribution of tasks and responsibilities with corresponding and novel opportunities for collaboration. Through workshops in various partner countries, we investigated what opportunities and obstacles (un)intentionally result from (energy) policies and regulations, and how the project could contribute to supporting new measures for energy poor households. During the project, successful new collaborations to reduce energy poverty were initiated in some countries, which will most likely continue beyond the lifetime of this project. The EnergyMeasures project has therefore led to a number of positive policy adjustments at different levels of government. In this section, we look in more detail at this form of capacity building and give some examples of how the EnergyMeasures project in partner countries has contributed to this. In order to do that, we take a closer look at the structural policy initiatives developed within the EnergyMeasures project in section 4.1. The following series of tables outline the types of policy workshops engaged in the seven focal countries.

Table 11 Policy workshops organised by the Belgium cluster

Date	Last Friday of every month
Location	Brussels
Organisations represented	De Sfeer, Genk – De Fakkel, Herentals – Alarm, Geel – Klimaatstem van MIA – Kempen – De Kring, Eeklo – Solidariteit zonder Grenzen, Gent – Ons Huis, Mol – My Trusto – De Ruimtevaart, Leuven – Energiesnoeiers Natuurpunt – VEKA – VREG – CREG – Fluvius – FEBEG – FOD Economie - Kabinet Demir – Kabinet Somers – Kabinet Van der Straeten – Groen – Ecohuis Antwerpen – Energient – Grootouders voor het Klimaat – Gezinsbond – IOK - LIGO Boom-Willebroek – STEBO – Geneeskunde voor het Volk – GBO ELZ Demerland – CAW Limburg – OCMW Mol – VVSG – Welzijnzorg – Vlaamse ombudsdienst – Federale ombudsman Energie
Number of attendees	Approximately 30 every meeting
Brief description of workshop	<p>'The Experts of SAAMO' is a participatory community work project in which people in poverty from all over Flanders - together with all kinds of stakeholders - meet monthly to discuss energy and climate policy and formulate policy suggestions. And this for more than 20 years ... A valuable combination of experience expertise and technical knowledge.</p> <p>In 2023, there were 10 meetings in which we reached 35 organizations and 290 participants (including 80 unique participants)</p> <p>We evaluated the Flemish energy poverty plan with the Flemish Energy and Climate Agency, discussed with FEBEG, the umbrella of energy suppliers how payment plans and accessibility of suppliers can be improved. The accessibility of energy desks was discussed as well as minimum energy standards for homes, the impact of energy efficient household appliances (Papillon) and how to track your energy consumption with the digital meter.</p> <p>In January, we had federal Energy Minister Tinne Van der Straeten visit us to discuss her policies and our expectations.</p>
Date	15-12-23
Location	Gent
Organisations represented	a very wide range of organizations and individuals committed to a socially just energy transition
Number of attendees	26 in workshop
Brief description of workshop	"Festival of equality" workshop. Theme: the role of people in energy poverty in the energy transition - how do we include everyone?

Table 12 Policy workshops organised by the Bulgarian partner

Date	21-11-2023
Location	Sofia
Organisations represented	University of Forestry, EnEffect
Number of attendees	15

Brief description of engagement	Lecture for students about energy efficiency, building renovation to alleviate energy poverty and improve quality of life.
Date	13-11-2023
Location	Sofia
Organisations represented	EnEffect, Citizens-led renovation initiative, Izgrei (First Bulgarian energy cooperative), NGO sector
Number of attendees	10
Brief description of engagement	Workshop for citizens and for experts on renovation policies, national initiatives, financing schemes.
Date	26-10-2023
Location	Burgas
Organisations represented	Burgas Municipality, EnEffect, Greenpeace Bulgaria, HOAs
Number of attendees	20
Brief description of engagement	Citizens engagement on the topic of energy communities, energy efficiency, benefits for vulnerable households from building renovation and RES solutions.
Date	08 – 10-12-2023
Location	Sofia
Organisations represented	EnEffect, School of Politics
Number of attendees	13
Brief description of engagement	School of Politics lecture for politicians on the topics of building renovation, EU and national legislation related to EE and RES, energy poverty.
Date	21-07-2023
Location	Borovetz
Organisations represented	EnEffect, School of Politics
Number of attendees	20
Brief description of engagement	Seminar for Rila municipality experts to involve citizens in the decision-making process in the field of energy efficiency at local level, organized with School of Politics, Borovets.
Date	06 – 08-06-2023
Location	Borovetz
Organisations represented	EnEffect, School of Politics
Number of attendees	19
Brief description of engagement	School of Politics workshop organized for NGOs on the topic of building renovation in the context of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) and leading European policies and practices.
Date	30-05-2023

Location	Sofia
Organisations represented	EnEffect, School of Politics
Number of attendees	15
Brief description of engagement	Workshop organized for municipal experts on the topic of building renovation, energy efficiency, regulatory framework, quality assurance, verification of results, project financing, and opportunities for local actions.
Date	27 – 28-11-2023
Location	Sofia and online
Organisations represented	EnEffect, Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, Ministry of Energy, Sustainable Energy Development Agency, EIB, municipalities, NGOs
Number of attendees	139
Brief description of engagement	The roundtable was held alongside the XVI National Conference of the Association of Bulgarian Energy Agencies, covering the policies and investments for a sustainable, efficient, and secure energy system. The roundtable marked the official beginning of the multi-level dialogue on the National Energy and Climate Plan, and resulted in a wide media coverage.
Date	01-03-2023
Location	Sofia and online
Organisations represented	EnEffect, Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, Ministry of Energy, Sustainable Energy Development Agency, World Bank, National Advisory Council on the Green Deal, municipalities, professional associations
Number of attendees	152
Brief description of engagement	There was a dedicated workshop on energy poverty at the national roundtable on sustainable energy financing supported by SMAFIN project. The event successfully engaged stakeholders from all relevant fields involved in the EE policymaking and implementation at the local level.
Date	29-11-2021
Location	Velingrad and online
Organisations represented	EnEffect, Bulgarian Development Bank, Fund of Funds, Energy Efficiency and RES Fund, commercial banks, Sustainable Energy Development Agency, NGOs, National Trust EcoFund
Number of attendees	95
Brief description of engagement	The national conference supported by H2020's BeSMART project was organized alongside the annual event of the Association of Bulgarian Energy Agencies and was a great opportunity to network on key initiatives related to energy poverty, as well as project financing, since the participation of representatives of different financing institutions contributed to intensive discussions on local EE project realization and support measures.
Date	16-03-2022

Location	Borovetz and online
Organisations represented	EnEffect, Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, Center for the Study of Democracy, municipalities, Greenpeace Bulgaria, Bulgarian Energy and Mining Forum, National Trust EcoFund
Number of attendees	130
Brief description of engagement	One of the main discussion pillars of the roundtable event for sustainable energy financing with the support of the H2020 SMAFIN project was “Unleashing financing for building renovation through involvement of energy poor households”. The key takeaways from the policy conference would later inform the development of policy recommendations for energy poverty alleviation.
Date	18-02-2021; 25-02-2021
Location	Sofia and online
Organisations represented	EnEffect, Deputy Prime Minister, Minister of Energy, MEPs, local authorities
Number of attendees	N/A
Brief description of engagement	EnEffect’s regional energy planning manual was presented to politicians from the national and local level at a conference held at two days at the Bulgarian national TV on the topic of the Green Deal and what it means to the municipalities, their EE planning, energy management, building renovation and energy poverty policies.
Date	12 – 13-11-2020
Location	Gabrovo and online
Organisations represented	Municipalities, EnEffect, Deputy Minister for Energy, Executive Director of the SEDA, BPIE, National Association of Municipalities in the Republic of Bulgaria, Bulgarian Construction Chamber, EERSF, NTEF, Decent Home Coalition, ZaZemiata
Number of attendees	90
Brief description of workshop	Special session in the conference of municipal energy efficiency network EcoEnergy “Towards the formulation of clear policies and measures for overcoming energy poverty in Bulgaria”

Table 13 Policy workshops organised by the Irish cluster

Date	15-02-2023
Location	MABS offices, Dublin
Organisations represented	UCC, MABS, ALONE, SvP, Age Action Ireland
Number of attendees	6
Brief description of workshop	Stakeholder workshop to effect policy change in the Irish policy landscape. Included discussion on how to leverage energy supplier funds with NGO and other organisational expertise dealing with energy poverty

Table 14 Policy workshop organised by the North Macedonian partner

Date	27-09-2023
Location	Hotel Holiday Inn, Skopje
Organisations represented	Habidom, Department of Housing in Ministry of Transport and Communications, Energy Sector in Ministry of Economy, Municipality of Karposh, Microfinance Institution Horizonti and Finerti – construction company
Number of attendees	12
Brief description of workshop	Discussion was made regarding the current Housing Law and Energy Efficiency Law and what improvements should be made in order the country to move forward.

Table 15 Policy workshops organised by the Polish partner

Date	11-12-2023
Location	Bielsko-Biała
Organisations represented	PNEC
Number of participants	30
Brief description of training	The workshop focused on the planning of measures to alleviate energy poverty. The definition of energy poverty, its causes and consequences, the current situation in Poland and Europe, the key role of local authorities, factors hindering the identification of the energy poor and the phases of the fight against this phenomenon were presented.
Date	23 – 24-10-2023
Location	Kraków
Organisations represented	PNEC
Number of participants	38 (onsite) + 64 (online)
Brief description of training	The meeting was mainly devoted to energy law, energy communities, and the opportunities for functioning in cities and municipalities from the perspective of recently updated Polish legislation. The strong interest in this subject, justified by the latest and planned changes in Polish law and new funding programs for the energy communities' creation and operation, influences energy poverty prevention by giving new technical and organizational solutions to reduce energy consumption, lower bill payments and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.
Date	11 – 12-05-2023
Location	Jadwisin
Organisations represented	PNEC
Number of participants	63

Brief description of training	The seminar 'Sustainable development of cities and municipalities on the road to climate neutrality' was an opportunity to expand knowledge in the field of energy transition, energy poverty prevention and citizen involvement. One session was dedicated to energy poverty and the helpful and impactful activities, using the results of EnergyMeasures project.
Date	19 – 20-05-2022
Location	Jadwisin
Organisations represented	PNEC
Number of participants	60
Brief description of training	The seminar 'Inclusive energy transition and climate protection in cities and municipalities' was an excellent opportunity to expand knowledge in the field of sustainable urban management, energy poverty prevention and citizen involvement. The presentation about EnergyMeasures aims was presented and the roundtable about energy poverty organised.

Table 16 Policy workshops organised by the Dutch cluster

Date	17-11-2022
Location	Tilburg – Het PON & Telos office
Organisations represented	The boards of energy cooperatives (both solar and wind energy), representatives of the province of South Holland, Het PON & Telos, Municipality of Eindhoven, Duneworks
Number of participants	11 participants and then a number (four) interested people from Het PON & Telos who would like to learn about this, but did not actively participate in the discussions.
Brief description of training	This was a business modelling workshop where we showed the boards a number of presentations about different business models and where they could then share experiences with each other.

Table 17 Policy workshops organised by the UK (Scottish) partner

Date	23-11-2023
Location	Energy Action Scotland Conference
Organisations represented	Wide ranging audience which included, Energy Action Scotland (NGO campaigning on overcoming energy poverty in Scotland) NHS Scotland, local municipalities, energy companies, NGO's, Scottish Government officials.
Number of participants	75
Brief description of training	The workshop was designed to impart participants with a strong understanding of the EnergyMeasures methodology and how it could help deliver policy level change in Scotland. This included a focus on the work of Tighean Innse Gall in the Outer Hebrides, who demonstrated pathways for

	<p>other groups to adopt, as well as case studies and further information from all EnergyMeasures partners, delivered by the Project Manager Dr Niall Dunphy, UCC. The workshop also heard from partners delivering Community Energy for Energy Solidarity (CEES), which was designed to further promote collaboration with another Horizon project (No. 101026972).</p> <p>Overall, the principle aims of promoting effective support for energy poor households, learning from and building on the success of EnergyMeasures were met. This was demonstrated in feedback from participants during the workshops on how they could take up examples of best practise offered.</p>
Date	11-10-2022
Location	Tighean Innse Gall offices, Stornoway
Organisations represented	Just Transition Commission and Secretariat
Number of participants	19
Brief description of training	<p>The Just Transition Commission operates independently, drawing on expertise and experience from leading figures in industry, business, trade unions, academia, and environmental and community groups. It works alongside bodies with related remits such as the Fair Work Convention and Poverty and Inequality Commission. The overall mission is a fair transition to net zero emissions in Scotland, undertaken in partnership with those impacted by the transition.</p> <p>The Commission visited Tighean Innse Gall specifically to hear about the work of EnergyMeasures in person. The Commission experts were keen to gain an understanding of our methodology of outreach and recruitment, support available, referral mechanisms and how we were able to demonstrate immediate savings for households, something which no other project in Scotland was able to achieve. They were in the process of drawing up their second report to Scottish Government, which was identifying best practise for engagement best practise and how to ensure equalities were considered.</p>
Date	05-07-2022
Location	Online: Teams meeting
Organisations represented	Comhairle nan Eilean Siar (local authority), NatureScot (Chair of group), Community Land Outer Hebrides Tighean Innse Gall
Number of participants	6
Brief description of training	<p>The Climate Change Working Group wished to find out about carbon emission advice and reduction projects linked to fuel poverty. As the only project in the islands which did have a direct benefit of providing advice, immediate reductions and alleviation of fuel poverty, EnergyMeasures provided the group with a briefing for them to develop their policies on the issues.</p>

4.1 Structural initiatives developed from the EnergyMeasures project

Section 2 of this deliverable focused mainly on the internal capacity building efforts of the project, while in section 3, we discussed policy and practice innovation as a means of external capacity building. Task 3.1 of the project focused on innovative governance initiatives to address the structural causes of energy poverty and Task 3.2 was aimed at formulating policy recommendations for addressing energy poverty. Task 3.3 was comprised a real-life case study in the Irish policy context where the issue of energy poverty was tackled through by means of a collaboration between the Irish project partners and cognate energy suppliers. Informative deliverables have been written of the course and outcomes of these three tasks (see D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, and D3.4)⁹. We highlight them because the case studies described in these deliverables contribute to external capacity building.

4.1.1 Emerging innovative governance & business instrument to address energy poverty (T3.1)

As mentioned, the aim of T3.1 was to explore, stimulate, and create innovative governance and business instruments to address energy poverty. In this task, preliminary interviews and three business modelling workshops (using a business model canvas to create value¹⁰) were held in three different partner countries: Ireland (UCC in the lead), Bulgaria (Eneffect in the lead) and in the Netherlands (Duneworks and Het PON & Telos in the lead). Participants in these business modelling workshops were setting up innovative and structural initiatives to combat energy poverty. The aim of these workshops was to collaboratively explore and clarify the value proposition of these initiatives, to explore and learn how each initiative has potential across different (local) contexts (up-scaling), who needs to be involved, and what sort of institutional conditions (policies, legislation, rules) are required for its continued success.

The business modelling workshops had different themes. In the Netherlands, a number of energy cooperatives were brought together who were looking for a more equitable distribution of their profits. In this, however, they are inhibited by certain Dutch laws and regulations. The business modelling workshop in Bulgaria focused on new financing instruments that support homeowners in starting renovation activities. In Ireland, the business modelling workshop focused on the potential of the so-called 'Third Sector'. This sector includes NGOs and sometimes voluntary organisations, working to tackle energy poverty. They are forced by legislation however, to have their volunteers professionalised, resulting in a reduction in available budget to support households in energy poverty. In this deliverable, it is not useful to discuss in detail the course of the three business workshops. For details about these workshops, we refer to the relevant deliverable 3.2. In this section we address those aspects that are relevant in light of external capacity building and the positive reception of the participants in the workshops, particularly in terms of the replicability and the upscaling potential, but also for identifying new forms of cooperation between organisations and governments.

By bringing together participants in the workshops and having them think about themes that fit within their innovative initiatives in an activating working format, the workshop leaders created additional knowledge about the complex governance context in relation to addressing energy poverty and knowledge transfer among the participants. The workshops stimulated awareness about the drivers and bottlenecks in the

⁹ For more information please see: <https://zenodo.org/communities/energymeasures/>

¹⁰ Osterwalder's Business Model Canvas informed effort in all of the workshops, and while the workshops tended to follow a more open-ended format for discussions, e.g., in NL it was used also to structure interview results.

institutional context within which the initiatives operate and about the use of a business model canvas to identify and explore value(s) within those initiatives. After each workshop, the participants completed an evaluation, which showed that they acknowledged the value of the workshop and found it valuable to learn from the experiences and approaches of other participants.

Although the cases in the workshops differed from each other, we can say something about external capacity building from the perspective of upscaling and replicability. A lesson learned is that it is important to add expert knowledge for upscaling and replication to (local) initiatives. Mutual trust is needed between the government(s) involved and initiatives, and it is necessary that objectives of both the governments involved and initiatives are well aligned. There is a strong notion that policy can build on what is happening in practice and support innovative structural initiatives that alleviate energy poverty. The practical experiences of innovative initiatives offer valuable points of departure for discussing how policy can be informed by locally initiated effective approaches (Breukers *et al.*, 2023).

4.1.2 *Energy poverty policy agenda and recommendations (T3.2)*

Deliverable 3.2 builds on D3.1 and provides tools for external capacity building. Although, as in the previous section, while we do not discuss the content in detail we do outline key aspect to provide context. The central question in this deliverable is: *How can multi-level policy arrangements address energy poverty in a way that leads to structural alleviation to the benefit of households experiencing energy poverty?* This question has been answered in 10 governance propositions, 3 recommendations at EU level, and serve a dual purpose. They aim to foster policies and institutional arrangements that directly connect to energy poverty alleviation by addressing issues such as housing, health, income, personal capabilities, and comfort of living. Beyond that, an agenda for policy renewal is presented, which involves recommendations for changes in the governance – *i.e.*, the way in which policies are developed, passed and implemented – at multiple levels so as to better reflect considerations of procedural justice, transparency, and inclusiveness in the policy making process (Breukers *et al.*, 2023). In order to make these 10 governance propositions and 3 recommendations at EU level, all partners contributed by sharing energy poverty policy updates in their country with the task leader (Duneworks). Working sessions were held during the General Assemblies and interviews and workshops were held with relevant policy staff in both North Macedonia and the Netherlands.

In order to promote structural changes in policies towards an improved alleviation of energy poverty, the EnergyMeasures project partners have actively attempted to contribute to and influence policy developments in their country, based on their expertise and the lessons learned as part of works done in EnergyMeasures. Depending on the positions and roles of the project partners, they have worked directly or indirectly with policy makers, governmental bodies, and other policy domain stakeholders in their efforts to actively contribute to policy improvements. These efforts include, amongst others, the work performed in WP2 (Household engagements) and WP3 (Policy and practice innovation). Partners have been active in policy contributions at all levels of government (local, regional, national) and across policy domains including energy policy, housing policy, renovation policy, social policy, and climate policy (Young *et al.*, 2023). The following series of tables outline the types of impacts made on the policy landscapes in the focal countries.

Table 18 Influence of EnergyMeasures on policy (national, regional or local) – Belgium

Country, region, municipality	Flemish government - ministry of internal affairs
Policy domain	Energy taxshift
Input of EnergyMeasures	Brainstorm on necessary conditions to protect vulnerable households from effects of taxshift - new (preventive) measures – how to reduce gas consumption.
Country, region, municipality	Flemish government - ministry of Energy
Policy domain	Reformation of interest-free loan for renovation to ‘Mijn Verbouwen’ (up to €60.000, 2,25% interest) with focus on housing quality and energy saving measures.
Input of EnergyMeasures	We continue to advocate a 0% loan for target group 4 (vulnerable households), We did so at a hearing in the Flemish Parliament where SAAMO was able to present its point of view.
Country, region, municipality	Federal government – Ministry of Energie
Policy domain	Social energy tariff for vulnerable households
Input of EnergyMeasures	The federal government has extended the social tariff during the energy crisis but abolished the measure from July 1, 23. 500.000 families are affected. The measure is being currently revised. SAAMO is involved as a stakeholder and has frequent consultations with the minister and her cabinet.
Country, region, municipality	Local, Flemish and federal government
Policy domain	Memorandum for each policy level following the upcoming elections (June and October) - a wide range of policy demands on social measures to address energy poverty, improve housing quality and include vulnerable people in the energy transition.
Input of EnergyMeasures	Using our knowledge of energy poverty and reaching out to vulnerable groups

Table 19 Influence of EnergyMeasures on policy (national, regional or local) – Bulgaria

Country, region, municipality	Bulgaria
Policy domain	Financing of EE projects under the National building renovation programme
Input of EnergyMeasures	Advocacy and engagement efforts supported by EnergyMeasures have contributed to the redesign of the traditional practice of providing 100% grants for the renovation of private multi-family residential buildings. Thus, the implementation of the national renovation program continues, but what is most significant this time is the long-advocated introduction of 20% co-financing component for Stage II, which started in June 2023. Notably, representatives of the key ministries managing the programme have repeatedly stated during roundtables and public events organized together with EnEffect that grant subsidies will be increasingly reduced, except for specific cases, such as for vulnerable households.
Country, region, municipality	Bulgaria
Policy domain	Condominium Act update

Input of EnergyMeasures	The threshold for decision making within HOAs to participate in the national building renovation programme has been decreased towards the end of 2023 (from 67% before, to 51% now), and they are enabled to open a common bank account in a commercial bank. In the previous renovation programme, however, there used to be a condition that 95% of the homeowners sign a declaration that they agree that construction works are carried out in their apartments. The fact is that there is still no functional mechanism which can ensure that all homeowners comply with the decision of the association
Country, region, municipality	Bulgaria
Policy domain	Energy poverty definition approved
Input of EnergyMeasures	Regulation on energy poverty was approved, in line with the position advocated at various events by EnEffect and EcoEnergy in Bulgaria. Amendments to the Energy Act were introduced, providing for a transition period from 1st of July 2024 to 31st of December 2025. During this period, energy-poor households would receive state support for their electricity bills. This definition is also supposed to enable the differentiation of homeowners eligible for extended support for participation in renovation programmes; however, there is still no mechanism for its practical implementation.
Country, region, municipality	Bulgaria
Policy domain	RES for households
Input of EnergyMeasures	The 1st call for the procedure Support for renewable energy for households under the NRRP ran from May to November 2023, which has followed the logic intended to be bolstered with the support of EnergyMeasures – the procedure has two components, offering a 70% grant, with 100% support for energy poor households.
Country, region, municipality	Gabrovo
Policy domain	Sustainable energy planning, urban development, EE projects implementation
Input of EnergyMeasures	Improvement of capacity of HOAs members, building owners, municipal experts, construction sector professionals. Support has been provided for the functioning of the Municipal center for energy efficiency to the Municipality of Gabrovo, operating as an information and consultancy point for citizens on all matters related to EE and RES. Gabrovo continues to be a forerunner in the field of sustainable energy policy implementations in Bulgaria, establishing the first energy community with the support of EnEffect. The municipality is already a winner of EU Green Leaf for 2021, CoM national ambassadors, member of Committee of Regions.
Country, region, municipality	Burgas
Policy domain	Sustainable energy planning, urban development, EE projects implementation
Input of EnergyMeasures	Thanks to regular engagement through trainings, seminars, public events organized, Burgas' municipal experts and authorities have repeatedly cited the collaborative work with EcoEnergy and EnEffect as crucial to

	their successful implementation of EE building renovation projects thanks to improved capacity. The participation in international events has contributed to the municipality’s bold steps in the local citizens engagement activities, and their entry and success in different competitions and calls for projects (EUFCF, RegioStars). The municipality is planning to develop energy communities utilizing attractive public sites (hospital and library), and continues working towards developing projects related to energy sufficiency, energy poverty alleviation, smart monitoring building systems, etc.
Country, region, municipality	Sofia
Policy domain	Sustainable energy planning, urban development, EE projects implementation, strategy
Input of EnergyMeasures	Sofia’s SECAP till 2030 was developed with the support of EnEffect in 2021 in line with the “Energy efficiency first” principle and taking into consideration key measures that can contribute to energy poverty alleviation. The municipality has been actively engaged in all sustainable energy financing roundtables, as well as other international activities coordinated by EnEffect in the area of municipal energy management, sustainable development, knowledge and skills building for EE.

Table 20 Influence of EnergyMeasures on policy (national, regional or local) – UK (Scotland)

Country, region, municipality	Scotland
Policy domain	Just Transition Commission: https://www.gov.scot/publications/making-future-initial-report-2nd-transition-commission/
Input of EnergyMeasures	<p>Following a briefing by EnergyMeasures and extensive whole day discussion with the Just Transition Commission, we helped directly influence their 2nd Report that ultimately concluded:</p> <p>Engagement, participation and equalities [Context]</p> <p>Effective engagement, participation and feedback are integral to the processes of developing plans and activities to achieve a just transition. The consideration of potential differing and disproportionate impacts on different communities (of interest and place) needs to be central to the work to ensure effective mitigation. Policies related to the transition are now a very live political issue, so there is an opportunity for active engagement to identify challenges and opportunities to advance the 'just' element of the transition. <i>However, such engagement will need to consider planning around sensitivities to reach those communities who are struggling as a result of austerity and the cost-of-living crisis, and who may find it difficult to engage in such a process.</i></p> <p>Systematic and inclusive stakeholder engagement:</p> <p><i>Relevant tools and networks to engage stakeholders should be identified and used by building on the work of grass roots community organisations and intermediary organisations that provide support.</i> Depending on the nature of the engagement strategies emerging from stakeholder analysis, capacity and resources may be prioritised to ensure that the most marginalised groups are engaged with, even if this is more resource intensive.</p>

4.1.3 *The Irish case; the policy context of energy poverty and collaboration between government and energy communities (T3.3)*

UCC and Energy Action (and latterly PNEC) collaborated with several energy companies in Ireland to devise a support programme for energy poor households, which was designed to complement and supplement the small-scale measures provided through EnergyMeasures. The programme built on the household identification and recruitment carried out in WP2 to select a cohort of households to be targeted for additional support including *e.g.*, remote heating control systems, hot water control systems, insulation, and boiler replacements. The small number of person-months allocated for this task related to the management and administration of the proposed initiative. The actual engagement with the households took place within the context of WP2, while the supports were provided by the participating energy company. For more detail on this effort see *D3.4 Case Study: energy company vulnerable household support pilot programme*.

5 Concluding remarks

This deliverable presented and summarised the internal and external capacity building steps taken by the partners to contribute to alleviating energy poverty. All partners contributed to making these steps transparent. By indicating which internal training and workshops they have given to update knowledge about alleviating energy poverty among those who worked on the EnergyMeasures project, we gained an insight into how necessary it is for professionals working with households in energy poverty to properly be aware of the issues that play a role in this complex societal problem. Knowledge on relevant aspects both at the level of the individual householders and in relation to the institutional context/governance are necessary for effectively addressing energy poverty. This includes knowledge about what it is like to live in (energy) poverty, technical knowledge about which energy-saving measures are most effective in certain situations, and/or the health risks of living in (energy)poverty. But also, for example, knowledge about interview techniques or how to best approach households facing energy poverty are important. What we could see is that in each of the seven countries where household engagements took place, there have been a variety of capacity building activities, ensuring that the knowledge and skills of those working on the project were up to par and, simultaneously, making sure that the project employees were able to make an impact.

Considering external capacity building, it is worth emphasising that that all partners have actively contributed to this. Partners have presented at conferences, organised webinars, given guest lectures, co-written publications, engaged with policy makers from the field. Nearly 4,000 households were engaged by the project. These are all households that have gained knowledge about their own energy-related behaviours and who have been given practical tools to reduce their consumption. They also have a more comfortable home due to the small energy-saving measures that were implemented during the project. In addition, in this deliverable we looked at the structural changes within the energy poverty policy field. We saw that the EnergyMeasures project has contributed to structural policy adjustments in all countries on both a large and small scale. To ensure that energy poverty remains a priority and that new policies are developed, it's vital to concentrate on capacity building with policymakers, researchers, and other professionals as the groundwork for emerging governance models that are more effective in addressing the issue of energy poverty. This, and the potential collaborative learning between these actors, provides a strong basis for greater impact and effective responses to the wicked problem of energy poverty.

6 References

- Breukers, S., van Duren, M., Young, J., van de Ven, D., & Boekelo, M. (2021). *Citizen views on policy needs for energy poverty alleviation*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.686944>
- Breukers, S., Young, J., & Ajdini, O. (2021). *Review of EU and national policy affecting energy vulnerabilities in the participating countries*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6869334>
- Breukers, S., Young, J., Lennon, B., Stanisheva, T., Tzanev, D., & Whittington, B. (2023). *Emerging innovative governance and business instruments to address energy poverty*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10371061>
- Dunphy, N. P. (2023). *Case Study: energy company vulnerable household support pilot programme (interim report)*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10459079>
- Dunphy, N. P. (2023). *Guidelines for user-centred business modelling workshops*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10459053>
- Dunphy, N. P. (2020). *Review of Methods of Identifying Energy Poor Households*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6867435>
- Dunphy, N. P., Quinlivan, L., & Lennon, B. (2020). *Guidelines for integrating behaviour change approaches while engaging energy poor*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6941342>
- Dunphy, N., Lennon, B., & Velasco-Herrejón, P. (2023). *Towards a Better Understanding of Energy Poverty*. In *Living with Energy Poverty. Perspectives from the Global North and South*. (pp. 275–281). Abingdon: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003408536-27>
- Saridaki, M., Velasco-Herrejón, P., & Quinlivan, L. (2022). *Initial report on energy consumption of participating households*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400852>
- Velasco-Herrejón, P., & Lennon, B. (2022). *Capacity Building*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10370878>
- Young, J., & Breukers, S. (2023). *Energy poverty policy agenda and recommendations*. EnergyMeasures H2020 Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10371381>